

Hepatoprotective and cardioprotective effects of empagliflozin in spontaneously hypertensive rats fed a high-fat diet

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ABSTRACT

A combination of liver and heart dysfunction worsens the prognosis of human survival. The aim of this study was to investigate whether empagliflozin (a sodium-glucose transporter-2 inhibitor) has beneficial effects not only on cardiac and renal function but also on hepatic function. Adult (6-month-old) male spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) were fed a high-fat diet (60% fat) for four months to induce hepatic steatosis and mild heart failure. For the last two months, the rats were treated with empagliflozin (empa, 10 mg.kg⁻¹.day⁻¹ in the drinking water). Renal function and oral glucose tolerance test were analyzed in control (n=8), high-fat diet (SHR+HF, n=10), and empagliflozin-treated (SHR+HF+empa, n=9) SHR throughout the study. Metabolic parameters and echocardiography were evaluated at the end of the experiment. High-fat diet feeding increased body weight and visceral adiposity, liver triglyceride and cholesterol concentrations, and worsened glucose tolerance. Although the high-fat diet did not affect renal function, it significantly worsened cardiac function in a subset of SHR rats. Empagliflozin reduced body weight gain but not visceral fat deposition. It also improved glucose sensitivity and several metabolic parameters (plasma insulin, uric acid, and HDL cholesterol). In the liver, empagliflozin reduced ectopic lipid accumulation, lipoperoxidation, inflammation and pro-inflammatory HETEs, while increasing anti-inflammatory EETs. In addition, empagliflozin improved cardiac function (systolic, diastolic and pumping) independent of blood pressure. The results of our study suggest that hepatoprotection plays a decisive role in the beneficial effects of empagliflozin in preventing the progression of cardiac dysfunction induced by high-fat diet feeding.

1. Introduction

Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD), or metabolic-associated fatty liver disease (MAFLD) represents a spectrum of diseases ranging from hepatocellular fat deposition to non-alcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) with or without fibrosis, which may lead to cirrhosis and increase the risk of hepatocellular carcinoma. [1]. Spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) are a long-established model of non-diabetic

hypertension with progressive hypertension-associated end-organ damage resembling human essential hypertension [2]. The feeding of SHR with a high-fat diet can induce not only fatty liver disease but also heart failure. Such combination of diseases leads to a substantial worsening of the prognosis for survival in human patients. Depending on the composition of the high-fat diet (i.e. addition of choline, cholesterol, fructose, sucrose, etc.) the degree of liver disease ranges from steatosis to steatohepatitis with varying degree of fibrosis [3]. A previous study [4]

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showed that diet-induced obesity is associated with reduced systolic and diastolic function in SHR but not in WKY rats. Similar results demonstrating adverse effects of high-fat feeding on cardiac function in SHR were recently published [5]. In addition, aging SHR develop signs of heart failure with preserved ejection fraction [6]. Thus, liver disease and heart failure may develop simultaneously after high-fat feeding in this experimental model, especially when started in adult rats with established hypertension.

Gliflozins (inhibitors of sodium glucose cotransporter-2; SGLT-2 inhibitors) are primarily antidiabetic drugs that reduce glucose and sodium reabsorption in the kidney. More recently they are also being investigated for the treatment of heart and renal failure, NAFLD, or some cardiovascular diseases even in non-diabetic patients. Beneficial cardiovascular effects of gliflozins, namely dapagliflozin, empagliflozin, or canagliflozin, have been demonstrated in large clinical trials, EMPAREG, CANVAS and CREDENCE in diabetic patients [7–9]. Later, the beneficial effects were also demonstrated in patients without diabetes - DAPA-CKD trial showed renoprotective effects of dapagliflozin in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD) [10] and similar findings were reported in EMPA-KIDNEY trial with empagliflozin [11]. Special attention has also been given to patients with chronic heart failure, where the DAPA-HF and EMPEROR-Reduced trials demonstrated beneficial cardiovascular effects and improved renal outcomes in heart failure patients with reduced ejection fraction [12]. Moreover, recent randomized clinical studies showed that empagliflozin treatment reduced hepatic fat accumulation not only in diabetic subjects, but also in NAFLD patients without T2DM [13,14].

Experimental data demonstrated the beneficial effects of gliflozins in diabetic rat and mouse models. In non-diabetic models of heart failure, beneficial effects of SGLT-2 inhibitors on cardiac function and/or remodeling after myocardial infarction (MI) were demonstrated in Sprague-Dawley rats [15–17], Fischer F344 rats [18], SHR with heart failure [5] and salt hypertensive Dahl rats [19]. There are conflicting data regarding the renal effects of gliflozins in non-diabetic experimental models. Renoprotective effects of gliflozins were found in Sprague-Dawley rats with heart failure [15], and in salt hypertensive Dahl rats [20], while ambiguous effects were found in rats subjected to 5/6 nephrectomy [21,22]. Animal studies have also shown beneficial effects of gliflozins in NAFLD because empagliflozin reduced hepatic lipid accumulation and ameliorated signs of NAFLD in mice models with dietary-induced obesity [23,24]. Our recent study in non-obese pre-diabetic hereditary hypertriglyceridemic (HHTg) rats [25] demonstrated reduced hepatic lipid accumulation accompanied by a decreased gene expression of lipogenic enzymes *Scd1*, *Fasn* and lipogenic transcription factor *Srebf1* as well as by altered expression of cytochrome P450 genes (*Cyp2e1*, *Cyp4a*) following empagliflozin administration. Recently, several experimental studies have analyzed the effects of SGLT-2 inhibitors in NAFLD and suggested ER stress, oxidative stress, low-grade inflammation, autophagy and apoptosis as key molecular mechanisms responsible for their hepatoprotective effects [26].

Therefore, we hypothesized that in SHR with high-fat diet-induced heart and liver disease, the chronic SGLT-2 inhibition would have beneficial cardiac, liver, and renal effects.

2. Methods

2.1. Animals and diet

Six-month-old male spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR) were used in the study. Rats were fed either a low-fat (SHR control, n=8) or a high-fat diet (SHR+HF, n=10) for four months. For the last two months, rats were treated with empagliflozin (SHR+HF+empa, n=9). All animals survived throughout the study (except one animal in the empagliflozin group, which died during the fourth week of empagliflozin treatment). The experimental design is shown in [Supplementary Figure 1](#). Animals were housed in groups of 2 rats/cage at 23 °C under a

12 h light/dark cycle, fed a standard (low-fat) diet for rats (Altromin-1320, Lage, Germany, 11% fat, 24% protein, 65% carbohydrates, 0.45% NaCl) or high-fat diet (Research Diets, D12492, 60% fat, 20% protein, 20% carbohydrates) and given tap water *ad libitum*. Empagliflozin (Jardiance, Boehringer, Ingelheim, Germany) at a dose of 10 mg/kg/day was administered in the drinking water for two months. The dose was chosen on the basis of previous data showing its efficacy in natriuresis and glycosuria [27,28]. The concentration of empagliflozin was adjusted weekly according to actual water intake. Body weight (BW) and food consumption were monitored throughout the experiment.

All procedures and experimental protocols were approved by the Ethical Committee of the Institute of Physiology, Czech Academy of Sciences (Protocol Nr. 39/2023), and complied with the European Convention on Animal Protection and Guidelines on Research Animal Use (Directive 2010/63/EU). All steps to reduce pain, suffering and distress during surgical procedures and the experimental interventions on the animals were taken in accordance with this experimental protocol (Protocol Nr. 39/2023).

2.2. Biochemical analysis

Before the start of empagliflozin treatment (week 0) and at the end of the study (week 8), an oral glucose tolerance (OGT) test was performed in overnight fasted animals. During OGT test, plasma glucose concentration was measured at 0, 30, 60, 120, and 180 minutes after the intragastric administration of glucose at a dose 3 g/kg of BW, and blood was collected from the tail vessels.

Three times during the experiment (at weeks –8, 0 and 8), animals were placed in individual metabolic cages for evaluation of renal function by 24-hour urine collection. Urinary protein, sodium, glucose, urea, and creatinine were measured. Urinary protein was measured by the Folin method using bovine serum albumin as a standard [29]. Plasma creatinine was measured by FUJI DRI-CHEM analyzer using appropriate slides for creatinine CRE-P III (Fujifilm Corp, Tokyo, Japan). Plasma urea was determined using a kit (Erba Lachema, Czech Republic). Lipoperoxidation products were assessed based on the levels of thiobarbituric acid-reactive substances (TBARS) by measuring the reaction with thiobarbituric acid. Serum levels of glucose, triglycerides, total and HDL-cholesterol were measured by commercially available kits (Erba-Lachema, Brno, Czech Republic). Non-esterified fatty acids (NEFA) levels were determined using an acyl-CoA oxidase-based colorimetric kit (Roche Diagnostics GmbH, Mannheim, Germany). Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) and aspartate aminotransferase (AST) enzyme activity were determined spectrophotometrically using commercially available kits (Roche Diagnostics, Mannheim, Germany). Serum concentrations of insulin, glucagon, leptin, hsCRP, TNF α , and MCP-1 were determined using appropriate rat ELISA kits (Mercodia, Uppsala, Sweden; MyBioSource, USA; eBioscience-Beder, Austria; BioVendor, Czech Republic; Invitrogen, Vienna, Austria). Insulin sensitivity in peripheral tissues was measured *ex vivo* in skeletal muscle or epididymal adipose tissue incubated in Krebs-Ringer buffer with or without insulin (250 μ U/mL). 14 C-U glucose incorporation into tissue glycogen or lipids was determined as previously described [30]. The concentration of 14,15-epoxyeicosatrienoic (EET) and 20-hydroxytetraenoic (HETE) acids in the liver was determined using rat ELISA kits (MyBioSource, USA). Animals were sacrificed at the end of the study, and plasma and tissue samples were collected and stored at –80 °C for further biochemical analysis.

2.3. Cardiac function measurement

Left ventricular (LV) geometry and function were assessed by echocardiography before the end of the study using a GE Vivid 7 Dimension (GE Vingmed Ultrasound, Horten, Norway) with a 12 MHz linear matrix probe M12L [31]. The Doppler echocardiographic parameters of mitral valve and pulmonary artery flows were also determined. Animals were anesthetized with 2% isoflurane (Forane, Abbott Laboratories,

Queenborough, UK) mixed with room air, placed on a heating pad, and their rectal temperature was maintained between 36.5 and 37.5 °C. Baseline 2D-mode and M-mode in the long and short axis of the left ventricle and mitral and pulmonary artery flow were recorded. Heart rate (HR) and the following parameters of LV geometry were assessed: end-diastolic and systolic LV cavity diameter (LVdD, LVdS), LV cavity length (LVLd, LVLs), LV cavity area in short axis (LVAd, LVAs), anterior wall thickness (AWTd, AWTs), and posterior wall thickness (PWTd, PWTs). Based on the above LV geometry, the following parameters were derived:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{fractional shortening (FS)} &= 100 * [(\text{LVdD} - \text{LVdS}) / \text{LVdD}]; \\ \text{relative wall thickness (RWT)} &= 100 * [(\text{AWTd} + \text{PWTd}) / \text{LVdD}]; \\ \text{stroke volume (SV)} &= (\pi / 3) * (\text{LVdD}^3 - \text{LVdS}^3); \\ \text{ejection fraction (EF)} &= 100 * \text{SV} / [(\pi / 3) * \text{LVdD}^3]; \\ \text{cardiac output (CO)} &= \text{SV} * \text{HR}; \\ \text{cardiac index (CI)} &= \text{CO} / \text{BW}. \end{aligned}$$

2.4. Blood pressure measurement

Systolic blood pressure was monitored during the study by the tail-cuff method (Haterras, USA, Maine). Moreover, direct BP measurement was performed at the end of the study in anesthetized rats cannulated before the experiment [32]. Briefly, a polyethylene cannula was implanted into the left carotid artery under 2.5% isoflurane anesthesia (PE 50). Blood pressure and heart rate (HR) were recorded using a pressure transducer and multichannel recorder (ADInstruments, Bella Vista, Australia).

2.5. Histological evaluation

Liver tissue samples were fixed in formaldehyde for 24 h, dehydrated, and embedded in paraffin. Hematoxylin-eosin and Van Gieson stained 4 µm sections were examined in a blind fashion. Liver parenchymal injury was scored according to Kleiner et al. [33] using NAFLD activity scores (NASs).

Kidneys from each group were sectioned longitudinally and processed for paraffin embedding. Multiple 4 µm thick sections were cut and stained with hematoxylin-eosin, PAS and Azan-Mallory trichrome stain for light microscopy. Images were captured with a digital camera by an experienced pathologist in a blind fashion. Renal damage, as determined by glomerulosclerosis index and tubulointerstitial injury, was assessed using the Nikon NIS-Elements AR 3.1 morphometric program (Nikon, Tokyo, Japan) as previously described [34,35].

The apical halves of the hearts were immersion fixed in 4% paraformaldehyde in phosphate buffer saline (PBS, pH 7.4) for 48 hours. After repeated rinses with PBS, the samples were dehydrated in an ascending ethanol series, cleared in xylene, and embedded in Paraplast. Serial sections were cut at 10 µm using a rotary microtome. Sections were alternatively stained with Alcian Blue / Hematoxylin-Eosin and Picrosirius Red using standard protocols. Images of the stained sections were captured on an Olympus BX51 upright microscope with a 20x objective and an Olympus DP 80 CCD camera. For Picrosirius Red staining, sections were scanned with an Olympus slide scanner at 20x magnification. Five representative fields per heart containing the left ventricular tissues, avoiding larger vessels, were exported using Olyvia viewing software and analyzed for percent fibrosis as described [36]. Myocyte damage scoring was performed on two representative fields per heart (papillary muscle and mid-ventricular circular layer) on Alcian Blue / Hematoxylin-Eosin stained sections. A semi-quantitative grading of severity was established as follows [36]: Grade 0 – normal myocyte appearance with no fibrosis; Grade 1 – less than 33% of myocytes showing pale cytoplasm suggesting lipid accumulation, with minimal fibrosis; Grade 2 – between one and two thirds of myocytes showing abnormal morphology, with some increase in extracellular matrix; Grade 3 – over 2/3 of abnormal myocytes, often with locally significant patches of perivascular and interstitial fibrosis. The images were

adjusted for display in Adobe Photoshop using the Adjust Levels function to equalize brightness and improve contrast, and Unsharp Mask filter (kernel size 3 pixels, sharpen intensity 50%) to improve the sharpness. All these transformations were applied on the whole image.

2.6. Gene expression analysis in the kidney

Frozen tissues were homogenized using MagNA Lyser Green Beads (Roche, Basel, Switzerland), and total RNA was isolated using Genelute Mammalian Total RNA Miniprep Kit (Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA). The amount and purity of RNA was checked using a NanoDrop ND 1000 spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Products, Wilmington, DE, USA). The integrity of total RNA was tested using an Agilent 2100 Bioanalyzer (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, CA). RNase-Free DNase Set (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) was used to remove residual DNA. Gene expression was measured on the LightCycler® 480 System (Roche) using HOT FIREPol® Probe qPCR Mix Plus (SolisBioDyne, Tartu, Estonia) and TaqMan® Gene Expression Assays (Life Technologies, Carlsbad, CA, USA). Exported raw data were analyzed using LinRegPCR software (version 2013.0) to determine C_t values (number of cycles needed to reach the threshold) and mean PCR efficiencies per amplicon (averaged efficiencies of individual samples amplified with a given TaqMan Gene Expression Assay). The values obtained were used for relative quantification by the modified 2^{-ΔΔCT} method, using PCR efficiency as the base of exponentiation. The data were normalized to the reference gene (B2M) selected by NormFinder software [37].

2.7. Statistical analysis

The data are presented as mean ± SEM. Statistical analysis was performed by one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) or repeated measures of ANOVA using the Graph-Pad Prism software (Graph Pad Software, San Diego, CA, USA). Differences were considered significant at the p < 0.05 level.

3. Results

3.1. The effects of high-fat diet and empagliflozin on body composition and food consumption

Food consumption decreased by 40% after the switch from the low-fat to the high-fat diet and remained stable throughout the experiment. Empagliflozin-treated SHR consumed the same amount of food as untreated SHR (Fig. 1A). High-fat diet feeding induced a significant increase in body weight in both untreated and empagliflozin-treated SHR compared with control SHR (Table 1, Fig. 1B). This increase in body weight was 14±4 and 13±4% in untreated animals and in empagliflozin-treated SHR on high-fat diet, respectively (Fig. 1B). Body weight gain was reduced in empagliflozin-treated group compared with untreated SHR+HF group from week 5 after the start of empagliflozin treatment, the final difference in body weight gain was 17±3 g (Fig. 1D). There was no change in relative heart weight after high-fat diet feeding, whereas the amount of visceral fat depots (perirenal and epididymal) was increased and the kidney weight was slightly decreased. Treatment with empagliflozin had no effect on any of these body parameters, but increased relative kidney weight (Table 1).

3.2. The effects of high-fat diet and empagliflozin on glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity

After eight weeks of high-fat diet feeding, both HF groups showed impaired glucose tolerance (Fig. 2A, C) as measured by the OGT test, and significantly increased insulinemia (Table 2). At this time point, i.e., before the start of empagliflozin treatment, both groups had similar body weight (379±11 vs. 395±10 g in SHR+HF vs. SHR+HF+empagliflozin, respectively), fasting serum glucose levels (4.8±0.1 vs. 5.0±0.2 mmol/

Fig. 1. The effect of empagliflozin treatment on daily food consumption (A) and cumulative body weight gain (B), systolic blood pressure (C) and body weight gain from the onset of empagliflozin treatment in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control, n=8) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF, n=10) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa, n=10) (red circles). @ $p < 0.05$ control group fed a low-fat diet vs. HF groups, * $p < 0.05$ SHR+HF vs. control group fed a low-fat diet, # $p < 0.05$ SHR+HF+empa vs. untreated high-fat group (SHR+HF). Data are means \pm SEM.

Table 1

Body parameters, systolic blood pressure and heart rate at the end of the study in untreated spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control), SHR fed with high-fat (SHR+HF) diet for 4 months and SHR treated with empagliflozin (SHR+HF+empa) for the last 2 months of high-fat diet feeding. Values are means \pm SEM; * $p < 0.05$ vs. control SHR; # $p < 0.05$ vs. untreated high-fat group.

	SHR-control	SHR+HF	SHR+HF+empa
n	8	10	9
Body weight (BW) (g)	372 \pm 5	424 \pm 6*	420 \pm 3*
Heart weight (g/100 g BW)	0.354 \pm 0.005	0.340 \pm 0.004	0.345 \pm 0.003
Perirenal fat weight (g/100 g BW)	1.170 \pm 0.063	2.391 \pm 0.098*	2.201 \pm 0.142*
Epididymal fat weight (g/100 g BW)	0.658 \pm 0.035	1.215 \pm 0.092*	1.271 \pm 0.100*
Kidney weight (g/100 g BW)	0.701 \pm 0.007	0.621 \pm 0.010*	0.673 \pm 0.007#
Liver weight (g/100 g BW)	3.599 \pm 0.048	3.236 \pm 0.052*	3.385 \pm 0.041*
Systolic blood pressure (mm Hg)	210 \pm 4	203 \pm 3	200 \pm 4
Heart rate (bpm)	343 \pm 11	347 \pm 9	330 \pm 8

L) and triglyceride levels (0.751 \pm 0.095 vs. 0.725 \pm 0.056 mmol/L). Although fasting glucose levels were not significantly affected by empagliflozin treatment (5.7 \pm 0.1 vs. 5.3 \pm 0.1 mmol/L), this treatment significantly improved glucose tolerance and decreased area under curve (AUC) during the OGT test (Fig. 2B, D). However, empagliflozin treatment did not attenuate the high-fat diet-induced impairment of

insulin sensitivity in skeletal muscle and visceral adipose tissue (Supplementary Fig. 2) or the high-fat diet-induced increase in serum insulin level (Table 2). High-fat diet feeding resulted in increased serum levels of pro-inflammatory MCP-1 and leptin, whereas hsCRP and TNF- α were not altered. Lipoperoxidation products TBARS were increased by the high-fat diet in the liver (Fig. 3C), but not in the heart or kidneys. Empagliflozin demonstrated its beneficial effects by reducing serum MCP-1 concentration and TBARS levels in the liver (Table 2).

3.3. The effects of high-fat diet feeding and empagliflozin on lipid metabolism and deposition

High-fat diet feeding significantly increased serum triglyceride and NEFA concentrations, whereas cholesterol was decreased and HDL-cholesterol was not affected (Table 2). Empagliflozin treatment had a beneficial effect on circulating lipids, as it decreased triglycerides and increased HDL cholesterol serum concentrations. In addition, the high-fat diet markedly elevated the accumulation of ectopic triglycerides and cholesterol in the liver and the accumulation of triglycerides in skeletal muscle, kidney, and myocardium (Table 2). Moreover, the reduced deposition of hepatic triglycerides after empagliflozin treatment was associated with increased concentrations of anti-inflammatory 14,15-EET and decreased concentrations of pro-inflammatory 20-HETE levels in the liver (Fig. 3). Neither the high-fat diet feeding nor empagliflozin treatment affected ALT or AST activities (Table 2).

3.4. The effects of high-fat diet feeding and empagliflozin on liver histology

No significant abnormality of liver parenchyma was detected in the

Fig. 2. Oral glucose tolerance test (A, B) and the area under the glycemic curve (AUC) (C, D) before the start of empagliflozin treatment (week 0) (A, C) and at the end of the study (week 8) (B, D) in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control, n=8) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF, n=10) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa, n=10) (red circles). * p < 0.05 vs. control group fed a high-fat diet. Data are means \pm SEM.

control SHR. After four months of high-fat diet feeding, both high-fat groups had significant metabolic changes characterized by mixed micro- and macro-vesicular steatosis of hepatocytes, accentuated centrilobularly. The hepatic steatosis observed in the SHR-HF group tended to be reduced in the empagliflozin-treated animals. No signs of inflammation or ballooning were found in both groups of high-fat-fed SHR (Table 4).

3.5. The effects of high-fat feeding and empagliflozin on cardiac function and blood pressure

Echocardiography was used to determine cardiac geometry and left ventricular (LV) systolic, diastolic, and pumping function. Doppler echocardiography of mitral flow revealed two different subgroups of SHR fed a high-fat diet with or without diastolic dysfunction based on the E/A ratio, which represents peak velocity blood flow from LV relaxation in early diastole (the E wave) to peak velocity blood flow in late diastole caused by atrial contraction (the A wave). In 50% of the rats (4 of 8 rats), the E/A ratio was greater than 2.3, whereas in the remaining animals it was less than 1.2 (Fig. 4C). Therefore, we decided to present the cardiac function parameters of SHR+HF rats as two subgroups, i.e., rats with high E/A ratio (light blue circles) and those with low E/A ratio (dark blue circles). In the high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup, this value was significantly increased compared with both the untreated SHR controls and the low E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup (3.14 ± 1.05 vs. 1.46 ± 0.05 and 1.08 ± 0.06 , respectively; Fig. 4C). The HF diet significantly increased the E/A ratio because of the significantly lower values of the A wave (Fig. 4B). In the rats fed HF diet and treated with empagliflozin, the E/A ratio was significantly lower compared with high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup (1.18 ± 0.13 vs. 3.14 ± 1.05) and did

not differ from the SHR+HF with low E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup and untreated SHR controls. Representative M-mode echocardiograms and mitral valve pulse-wave Doppler showing E (early filling) and A (atrial contraction) wave changes in these subgroups are shown in the lower panel of Fig. 4. Finally, neither HF diet alone nor its combination with empagliflozin treatment affected other parameters of mitral and pulmonary artery flow in SHR (Table 3).

Table 3 also shows left ventricular geometry at the end of the study. HF diet significantly increased systolic left ventricular diameter (approximately by 12%) and slightly (but not significantly) increased diastolic anterior wall thickness and posterior wall thickness (approximately by 8–13%) in both the high and low E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroups. Empagliflozin did not affect left ventricular dimensions at systole, but significantly increased diastolic left ventricular diameter to 8.32 ± 0.38 mm compared with 7.83 ± 0.27 mm in untreated SHR controls and normalized diastolic AWT and PWT.

The aforementioned changes in left ventricular geometry were reflected in a significant decrease in left ventricular systolic function expressed as fractional shortening and ejection fraction in all HF diet-fed groups (Fig. 5). However, empagliflozin treatment significantly increased fractional shortening by 14% compared with the high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup. Neither HF diet alone nor its combination with empagliflozin treatment affected relative wall thickness (Fig. 5C).

In addition, the HF diet significantly decreased heart rate (by 22%) in the high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup (Fig. 6A). In the low E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup and empagliflozin-treated SHR+HF group, heart rate was significantly higher than in the high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup and reached the values of untreated SHR controls. Stroke volume reached 0.38 ± 0.03 mL in untreated SHR controls and was slightly decreased in both SHR+HF subgroups (0.34 ± 0.03 and 0.36 ± 0.07 mL,

Table 2

Metabolic parameters in serum and tissues measured at fed state at the end of the study in untreated spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control), SHR fed with high-fat diet for 4 months (SHR+HF), and SHR treated with empagliflozin (SHR+HF+empa) for last 2 months of high-fat diet feeding. Values are means \pm SEM; * $p < 0.05$ vs. SHR-control; ** $p < 0.01$ vs. control group fed a low-fat diet, *** $p < 0.001$ vs. control group fed a low-fat diet, # $p < 0.05$ vs. untreated high-fat group, ## $p < 0.01$ vs. untreated high-fat group.

	SHR-control	SHR+HF	SHR+HF+empa
Triglycerides (mmol/L)	0.58 \pm 0.02	0.72 \pm 0.03*	0.59 \pm 0.02#
Cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.69 \pm 0.07	1.48 \pm 0.05*	1.59 \pm 0.04
HDL-cholesterol (mmol/L)	0.50 \pm 0.01	0.50 \pm 0.01	0.56 \pm 0.01**
NEFA (mmol/L)	0.48 \pm 0.02	0.61 \pm 0.03*	0.60 \pm 0.02*
Uric acid (mmol/L)	82.3 \pm 3.4	69.4 \pm 1.9*	55.7 \pm 2.4**
Insulin (nmol/L)	0.383 \pm 0.032	0.616 \pm 0.066*	0.505 \pm 0.050
Glucagon (pg/mL)	348 \pm 36	414 \pm 79	446 \pm 57
Non-fasting glucose (mmol/L)	6.24 \pm 0.11	6.93 \pm 0.17	6.87 \pm 0.15
ALT (mmol/L)	2.12 \pm 0.10	1.43 \pm 0.07	2.16 \pm 0.23
AST (mmol/L)	4.74 \pm 0.22	4.12 \pm 0.12	4.40 \pm 0.30
Creatinine (mmol/L)	21.8 \pm 0.8	22.1 \pm 0.7	19.7 \pm 0.8
Na ⁺ (mmol/L)	139 \pm 1	139 \pm 1	140 \pm 1
Cl ⁻ (mmol/L)	103.2 \pm 0.5	104.5 \pm 0.2	105.1 \pm 0.5
MCP-1 (ng/mL)	8.08 \pm 0.55	10.46 \pm 0.76**	8.01 \pm 0.33##
Leptin (ng/mL)	3.63 \pm 0.49	10.18 \pm 0.64***	8.71 \pm 0.77***
hsCRP (nmol/L)	2.99 \pm 0.27	2.16 \pm 0.22	2.34 \pm 0.14
TNF α (pg/mL)	2.32 \pm 0.27	3.44 \pm 0.94	2.44 \pm 0.28
KIM-1 (pg/mL)	644 \pm 105	823 \pm 102	751 \pm 120
NGAL (μ g/mL)	0.77 \pm 0.06	0.93 \pm 0.08	1.19 \pm 0.09**
Triglycerides in kidneys (mmol/g)	1.177 \pm 0.064	1.691 \pm 0.054**	1.694 \pm 0.106**
Triglycerides in heart (mmol/g)	1.8 \pm 0.088	2.313 \pm 0.128*	2.183 \pm 0.179*
Triglycerides in muscles (mmol/g)	0.541 \pm 0.07	1.359 \pm 0.119*	1.396 \pm 0.117*
TBARS in kidneys (ng/mg protein)	59.6 \pm 5.1	52.7 \pm 3.4	46.1 \pm 4.0
TBARS in heart (ng/mg protein)	307 \pm 38	406 \pm 41	365 \pm 10

HDL – high-density; NEFA – non-esterified fatty acids; ALT – alanine aminotransferase; AST – aspartate aminotransferase; MCP – monocyte chemoattractant protein; hsCRP – human C-reactive protein; TNF α – tumor necrosis factor α , KIM-1 – kidney injury molecule-1, NGAL – neutrophil gelatinase associated lipocalin

respectively). Empagliflozin increased stroke volume in the SHR+HF group to 0.43 \pm 0.06 mL, but the difference did not reach statistical significance compared with both untreated SHR+HF subgroups (Fig. 6B). The above-mentioned variables (heart rate and stroke volume) influenced the values of the derived LV pumping function parameters, i. e., cardiac output and cardiac index. The HF diet significantly decreased their values in the high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup. In the low E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup and the empagliflozin-treated SHR+HF group, cardiac output and cardiac index were significantly higher than in the high E/A ratio SHR+HF subgroup and reached the levels of untreated SHR controls (Fig. 6C,D). There was no difference in cardiac injury score between the examined groups, whereas empagliflozin substantially reduced the collagen-positive area (Table 4).

These results suggest that empagliflozin treatment prevented the progression of cardiac dysfunction (both systolic and diastolic) induced by high-fat feeding and restored cardiac parameters to values found in control SHR rats fed a low-fat diet.

During the experiment, there was no effect of either high-fat diet or empagliflozin on tail-cuff systolic blood pressure (Fig. 1C). Similarly, no differences in BP were observed between experimental groups during the direct BP measurement in anesthetized rats at the end of the study. Consistent with this, heart rate did not differ among the groups at the

end of the study (Table 1).

Our correlation analysis revealed several important factors related to left ventricular systolic function. Table 5 shows those parameters that had a significant correlation: relative liver weight, relative perirenal fat weight, plasma cholesterol, plasma leptin, liver triglycerides, liver cholesterol and liver TBARS, suggesting a close interrelationship between heart and liver function.

3.6. The effect of high-fat diet feeding and empagliflozin on renal markers and kidney function

Glucose excretion was three orders of magnitude higher in empagliflozin-treated SHR than in untreated rats, suggesting an effective blockade of SGLT-2 transporter (1514 \pm 253 in SHR+HF+empa vs. 3.7 \pm 1.4 in SHR+HF, μ mol/24 h, $p < 0.001$). With respect to renal function, the high-fat diet did not affect any of the renal parameters evaluated (diuresis, proteinuria, plasma urea or plasma creatinine) during or at the end of the study (Fig. 7 and Table 2). None of these parameters were significantly changed by empagliflozin treatment, except for serum uric acid, which was significantly reduced in the empagliflozin-treated group compared with the untreated high-fat diet fed group at the end of the study (Table 2). The lack of an effect of empagliflozin on functional parameters was confirmed by histological evaluation of kidney sections – neither glomerulosclerosis index nor tubulointerstitial injury differed between the three experimental groups (Table 4). Moreover, analysis of gene expression of several markers of inflammation (TGF- β , TNF- α), extracellular matrix (collagen, fibronectin), and cytoskeleton (nephrin 1, nephrin 2) did not reveal any beneficial effects of empagliflozin treatment (Supplementary Figure 5). Kidney injury markers are also consistent with our functional data - KIM-1 levels were unchanged, whereas NGAL was increased in the empagliflozin-treated SHR+HF group, which corresponds to a trend toward higher proteinuria in this group. Moreover, no effect of empagliflozin on renal lipoperoxidation products (TBARS) was observed (Table 2).

4. Discussion

In our complex *in vivo* study, which evaluated cardiac, renal and liver function, we have demonstrated the beneficial effects of empagliflozin in SHR fed a high-fat diet, a non-diabetic model of heart failure and NAFLD. These effects were mainly hepatoprotective and cardioprotective. Body weight gain were reduced by empagliflozin treatment. In the liver, both triglycerides and TBARS were reduced. In addition, reduced hepatic triglyceride deposition was associated with increased anti-inflammatory 14,15-EET and decreased pro-inflammatory 20-HETE levels in the liver. In the heart, empagliflozin treatment prevented the progression of high-fat diet feeding-induced cardiac dysfunction (both systolic, diastolic and pumping) and restored cardiac parameters to levels found in control SHR rats fed a low-fat diet.

Regarding body parameters, a significant increase in body weight and visceral adiposity was observed after high-fat diet feeding, consistent with the increased caloric intake (60% fat in the diet). This was associated with increased hepatic triglyceride and cholesterol levels. Unexpectedly, we did not observe a reduction of visceral fat mass after empagliflozin treatment. This is rather surprising, because most studies have shown a significant effect of gliflozins on the body weight or fat mass in non-diabetic animals [27,38], although there were studies in which no effect on body weight was observed [39–41]. One of the possible factors could be a relatively low dose of empagliflozin used in our study or a relatively short duration of study. Another possibility is the lack of hyperphagia in the present study, which has been previously demonstrated by several researchers, including us [27,42]. One must also bear in mind that all these models are non-diabetic and therefore the effects of SGLT-2 inhibition may not be so profound [41]. On the

Fig. 3. The effect of empagliflozin treatment on liver triglycerides (A), thiobarbituric acid-reactive substances - TBARS (B), 14,15-EET (C), and 20-HETE (D) in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa) (red circles). Data are means \pm SEM, $n=7-10$. Epoxyeicosatrienoic acid - EET, hydroxyeicosatetraenoic acid - HETE.

other hand, a reduction in body weight gain was observed only after 5 weeks of empagliflozin treatment, with the final difference between untreated and empagliflozin-treated HF groups being 17 g. A likely explanation for the delayed effect of empagliflozin on body weight could be that we used animals that were 10 months old at the end of experiment, in which body weight does not continue to increase as rapidly as in younger rats.

Our tail-cuff blood pressure measurements showed no effect of high-fat diet. This is in agreement with a previous study [4], which showed that obesity induced by high-fat diet feeding in SHR was not associated with an increase of blood pressure. On the other hand, Lee et al. [5] reported that empagliflozin treatment reduced systolic blood pressure by 30 mm Hg (from 115 mm Hg to 83 mm Hg, surprisingly low values for this hypertensive rat strain) in SHR rats fed with high-fat diet. However, these values were probably obtained during echocardiographic or electrocardiographic measurements under anesthesia. Moreover, their treatment lasted 12 weeks with a higher dose of empagliflozin (20 mg/kg/day) and a different type of high-fat diet. Blood pressure changes following SGLT-2 inhibitors in humans are mild, reaching a decrease of 4–6 mm Hg. Telemetric measurement would have been more appropriate to capture such small differences, but unfortunately this was not done in this study. Nevertheless, the lack of BP lowering effect is in line with the absence of changes in relative heart weight at the end of our study.

An increase in relative kidney weight was observed after

empagliflozin treatment. This phenomenon, often reported with SGLT-2 inhibitors, is attributed to tubular dilatation due to SGLT-2-induced diuresis and/or due to tubular cell hypertrophy [43,44]. Renal function was not improved by empagliflozin treatment – there was no change in proteinuria, plasma creatinine and plasma urea during the study. In addition, markers of renal injury (KIM-1 and NGAL), as well as gene expression of markers of inflammation (TGF- β , TNF- α), extracellular matrix (collagen, fibronectin) and cytoskeleton (nephrin 1, nephrin 2) were either unchanged or worsened. Our previous study in three non-diabetic experimental models of chronic kidney disease [39] also showed no beneficial effects of empagliflozin on renal functions. This is consistent with the results of a shorter (eight-week) study in patients with focal segmental glomerulosclerosis, who also did not benefit from dapagliflozin treatment in terms of renal hemodynamic function or proteinuria [45]. Moreover, the DAPA-HF clinical trial demonstrated no significant difference in the incidence of renal composite endpoints in heart failure patients treated with dapagliflozin [46], and the absence of renal changes induced by empagliflozin was also demonstrated in an experimental heart failure model [43]. It cannot be excluded that the main issue is the duration of treatment. Therefore, long-term experimental studies are needed to test this hypothesis.

From the point of view of cardiac function, empagliflozin has been demonstrated to attenuate serious heart failure outcomes in patients with both reduced and preserved ejection fraction (HF_rEF and HF_pEF, respectively) and to reduce the risk of cardiovascular death or

Fig. 4. The peak velocity blood flow from LV relaxation in early diastole (the E wave) (A) and in late diastole caused by atrial contraction (the A wave) (B), and the E/A ratio (C) in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control, n=8) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF, n=8) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa, n=8) (red circles). The SHR+HF group was divided into two subgroups based on the low (dark blue) and high (light blue) E/A ratio. Data are mean \pm SD. Lower panel - Representative M-mode echocardiograms and mitral valve pulse-wave Doppler showing E (early filling) and A (atrial contraction) wave changes in these subgroups.

Table 3

Doppler echocardiography of mitral and pulmonary artery flow and the geometry of the left ventricle measured at the end of the study in untreated control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR), SHR fed with high-fat diet (HF) for 4 months, and SHR treated with empagliflozin (empa, 10 mg/kg/day) for the last 2 months of HF treatment. The group of SHR+HF was divided into two subgroups based on the low and high E/A ratio (see Fig. 4).

	SHR	SHR+HF		SHR+HF+Empa
		High E/A	Low E/A	
n	8	4	4	8
Mitral flow				
IVCT (ms)	17.9 \pm 1.9	18.5 \pm 1.3	20.0 \pm 3.4	17.8 \pm 2.0
ET (ms)	71.3 \pm 6.0	69.5 \pm 4.1	69.8 \pm 3.9	68.3 \pm 4.9
IVRT (ms)	29.8 \pm 1.5	30.8 \pm 2.1	30.0 \pm 2.9	28.0 \pm 3.3
Pulmonary artery flow				
Vpa _{max} (m/s)	90.1 \pm 4.4	91.0 \pm 7.6	95.0 \pm 8.4	97.4 \pm 6.4
AT (ms)	19.9 \pm 3.6	17.5 \pm 2.1	18.0 \pm 3.7	19.9 \pm 4.6
ETpa (ms)	81.8 \pm 5.8	80.0 \pm 5.9	78.3 \pm 3.9	77.8 \pm 5.2
Geometry				
AWTd (mm)	2.24 \pm 0.15	2.42 \pm 0.35	2.43 \pm 0.16	2.27 \pm 0.17
LVDd (mm)	7.83 \pm 0.27	7.91 \pm 0.28	7.96 \pm 0.43	8.32 \pm 0.38*
PWTd (mm)	2.13 \pm 0.14	2.41 \pm 0.38	2.31 \pm 0.10	2.17 \pm 0.11
AWTs (mm)	3.04 \pm 0.17	3.12 \pm 0.30	3.06 \pm 0.08	3.03 \pm 0.22
LVDs (mm)	4.92 \pm 0.27	5.52 \pm 0.41*	5.49 \pm 0.18*	5.51 \pm 0.34*
PWTs (mm)	3.15 \pm 0.18	3.08 \pm 0.34	3.06 \pm 0.08	3.09 \pm 0.14

n, number of rats; AWTd, diastolic anterior wall thickness; LVDd, diastolic LV diameter; PWTd, diastolic posterior wall thickness; AWTs, systolic anterior wall thickness; LVDs, systolic LV diameter; PWTs, systolic posterior wall thickness; RWT, relative wall thickness; IVCT, isovolumic contraction time; ET, ejection time; IVRT, isovolumic relaxation time; Vp_{max}, peak velocity; AT, acceleration time; ETpa, pulmonary artery ejection time. Values are means \pm SD; *p<0.05 vs. SHR.

hospitalization for heart failure, regardless of the presence or absence of diabetes [47–49]. In the present study, we demonstrated that four-month feeding a high-fat diet reduced LV systolic and in 50% of

SHR also diastolic function. In addition, empagliflozin treatment normalized cardiac output and cardiac index in SHR fed a high-fat diet compared with untreated SHR controls. The beneficial effect of empagliflozin on LV function may be attributed to increased stroke volume (due to increased filling volume as documented by enlarged diastolic LV diameter) and increased heart rate. These findings are consistent with the study by Lee et al. [5] who demonstrated that empagliflozin improved high-fat diet-induced LV dysfunction in older SHR. Other studies have also reported that empagliflozin is effective in improving diastolic function, i.e., it can attenuate the progression of HFpEF in diabetic and/or obese rat models [50,51]. Conversely, SGLT-2 inhibitors had no effect on the LV systolic function in several rat models with established diabetes and/or obesity [52–57]. Finally, empagliflozin attenuated LV collagen-positive area, which is consistent with studies performed in rats with cardiorenal syndrome [21] (post-ischemic heart failure [16] or various models of hypertension [22, 59, 67]).

In non-diabetic and/or non-obese rats, empagliflozin favorably affected the adverse remodeling and impaired cardiac function after myocardial infarction [5,15,58] and slowed the progression of HFpEF (attenuated diastolic dysfunction) in rats with angiotensin II-dependent hypertension [59]. Conversely, empagliflozin did not improve the LV systolic function in various hypertensive rat strains with established hypertension [25,27,40,59]. Overall, SGLT-2 inhibitors slow the progression of heart failure. Although, it seems that their cardioprotective action is limited in rat models with advanced hypertension, diabetes, or obesity, our study clearly demonstrated a beneficial effect of empagliflozin in a hypertensive rat model fed a high-fat diet feeding.

Based on our metabolic results, empagliflozin treatment improved the deterioration of glucose tolerance induced by high-fat diet, although our model was non-diabetic. Thus, SGLT-2 inhibitors are able to protect against the development of prediabetic states induced by high-fat diet feeding. The reduction in insulin, leptin and also NEFA levels may contribute to the improved insulin sensitivity after empagliflozin administration. In our study, empagliflozin had beneficial effects on

Fig. 5. The left ventricular fractional shortening (A), ejection fraction (B), and the relative wall thickness (C) in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control, $n=8$) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF, $n=8$) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa, $n=8$) (red circles). The SHR+HF group was divided into two subgroups based on the low (dark blue) and high (light blue) E/A ratio. Data are mean \pm SD.

serum lipids.

Contrary to the parallel increase in total and HDL-cholesterol following the high-fat diet feeding, which was demonstrated in mice by Andreadou [60], we found a mild increase in triglycerides but a slight decrease in total cholesterol, the finding similar to other studies [61], with no significant change in HDL-cholesterol in SHR. These changes in serum lipid levels were relatively small but were associated with substantial ectopic accumulation of both cholesterol and triglycerides in the liver. Consequently, it could be assumed that the high-fat diet feeding affects metabolism, regulation, accumulation and transport of lipids. Therefore, one of the reasons why total and HDL-cholesterol levels does not go in parallel could be that cholesterol is accumulated in the liver while HDL-particles maintain their transport capacity for cholesterol.

The present study showed the important effect of empagliflozin on ectopic lipid deposition; i.e., triglyceride accumulation was reduced in

the liver while it was not affected in other tissues (kidney, heart and skeletal muscle). Thus, empagliflozin may protect against the development of NAFLD. The mechanism involved in the hypolipidemic effect of empagliflozin on the liver is probably decreased lipogenesis and attenuated lipid transport into cells. In our previous study [25], empagliflozin treatment modulated the expression of enzymes and transcription factors involved in lipogenesis and lipid storage, including *Scd1*, *Fas*, *Srebp1* and *Pparg*, which could be one of the possible mechanisms of hepatoprotection mediated by SGLT-2 inhibitors. We also speculate whether the transcription factor nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (Nrf2) and fibroblast growth factor 21 (FGF21) may contribute to the improvement of hepatic lipid metabolism and can alleviate oxidative stress in the liver, as has been shown in our previous study [25]. Consistent with our findings, empagliflozin attenuated the development of NAFLD in mice fed a high-fat diet [62] by reducing the expression of lipogenic genes (*Fas*, *Srebp1c* and *Pparg*) and genes involved in endoplasmic reticulum stress. In another study in Apo^{-/-} mice fed a high-fat diet [23], empagliflozin also attenuated NAFLD progression by reducing hepatic expression of lipogenic enzymes and inflammatory markers, primarily MCP-1. To our knowledge, neither of these studies in mice fed a high-fat diet evaluated hepatic triglyceride and cholesterol accumulation. Recently, it has been reported that treatment with empagliflozin effectively lowered liver fat content in diabetic patients [63].

Since low-grade chronic inflammation plays an important role in the development and progression of NAFLD, the potential anti-inflammatory effects of gliflozin have also been recently investigated. In the present study, empagliflozin treatment decreased circulating pro-inflammatory markers, in particular MCP-1, which contributes to the accumulation of macrophages in liver and adipose tissue, influences the generation of other inflammatory factors, and further potentiates inflammatory processes. In addition to MCP-1, our results indicate that the anti-inflammatory effects of empagliflozin are related to the bioactive lipid mediators 14,15-EET and 20-HETE, which are CYP450-derived arachidonic acid metabolites. While 14,15-EET has anti-inflammatory, trombotic and angiogenic properties, 20-HETE have pro-inflammatory effects [64]. Little is actually known about the effects of 14,15-EET and 20-HETE on fatty liver, but these bioactive arachidonic acid metabolites play an important role in the regulation of hepatic glucose and lipid metabolism. It has been suggested that 14,15-EET may be involved in the reduction of hepatic triglyceride accumulation. The *in vitro* study with HepG2 cells demonstrated that 14,15-EET treatment protected HepG2 cells against palmitic acid-induced inflammation and oxidative stress through attenuation of NF- κ B/JNK signaling pathways and NADPH oxidase expression [65]. The effect of empagliflozin on these bioactive lipid metabolites has not yet been investigated. Our present study demonstrated substantial effect of empagliflozin treatment on EETs and HETEs in the liver, i.e., empagliflozin decreased pro-inflammatory 20-HETE while increasing anti-inflammatory 14, 15-EET, which together may contribute to further improvement of liver function. This is consistent with our previous study in hereditary hypertriglyceridemic rats, a model of prediabetes, in which empagliflozin treatment was associated with the aforementioned changes in the expression of the cytochrome P450 family proteins involved in the pathogenesis of NAFLD, particularly Cyp2e1 and Cyp4a [25]. Thus, empagliflozin may directly affect some members of the cytochrome P450 family, contributing to the hepatoprotective effects.

Our results revealed that empagliflozin induced beneficial changes of several important metabolic factors (ectopic lipid accumulation, lipoperoxidation, oxidative stress, 14,15-EETs and 20-HETEs) which were associated with the improvement of left ventricular systolic function (ejection fraction and fractional shortening). Most of these metabolic parameters were related to liver function, suggesting its direct or indirect influence on cardiac function. The authors suggest that the cardioprotective effects are secondary to the hepatoprotective effects. However, future studies are necessary to prove this hypothesis.

In conclusion, our study demonstrated combined hepato- and

Fig. 6. Heart rate (A), stroke volume (B), cardiac output (C), and cardiac index (D) in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control, n=8) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF, n=8) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa, n=8) (red circles). The SHR+HF group was divided into two subgroups based on the low (dark blue) and high (light blue) E/A ratio. Data are mean \pm SD.

Table 4

Histological evaluation of liver, kidneys and heart at the end of the study in untreated spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control), SHR fed with high-fat (SHR+HF) diet for 4 months and SHR treated with empagliflozin (SHR+HF+empa) for last 2 months of high-fat diet feeding. Values are means \pm SEM; * p <0.05 vs. control SHR; *** p <0.001 vs. untreated high-fat group.

LIVER	SHR-control	SHR+HF	SHR+HF+empa
Steatosis	0	0.9 \pm 0.1***	0.67 \pm 0.17**
Inflammation	0	0	0
Ballooning	0	0	0
NAFLD score	0	0.9 \pm 0.1***	0.67 \pm 0.17**
KIDNEY			
Glomerulosclerosis index	0.055 \pm 0.016	0.054 \pm 0.020	0.060 \pm 0.015
Tubulointerstitial injury	0.050 \pm 0.015	0.090 \pm 0.022	0.081 \pm 0.032
HEART			
Cardiac score	1.8 \pm 0.25	2.5 \pm 0.26	2.1 \pm 0.23
Collagen positive area (%)	2.22 \pm 0.17	1.5 \pm 0.21*	1.01 \pm 0.17***

cardioprotective effects of empagliflozin in a model of hepatic steatosis and heart failure without adverse effects on renal function. Thus, from a clinical perspective, empagliflozin may be beneficial for patients with liver disease combined with heart failure and *vice versa*.

Table 5

Pearson correlation of fractional shortening and ejection fraction with various body and metabolic parameters; numbers are values of Pearson r coefficient, * p <0.05, ** p <0.01, n =24.

	Liver weight	Perirenal fat	Plasma cholesterol	Plasma leptin	Liver triglycerides	Liver cholesterol	Liver TBARS
	g/100 g BW	g/100 g BW	mmol/L	mmol/L	mmol/L	mmol/L	ng/mg protein
Fractional shortening (%)	0.637**	-0.634**	0.362 NS	-0.669**	-0.647**	-0.643**	-0.391*
Ejection fraction (%)	0.643**	-0.583**	0.440*	-0.545**	-0.672**	-0.634**	-0.389*

5. Limitation of the study

In addition to the issues mentioned in the discussion above, the authors are aware of several limitations of the study.

Transcriptomic analysis of the changes in differentially expressed genes (DEGs) after empagliflozin administration in different tissues, which has been published in SHR rats treated with empagliflozin (but on normal chow), would certainly be interesting, but was not the aim of our study. In fact, Tan et al. [66] showed that empagliflozin exerted major effects on kidney, white adipose tissue and lungs. These latter two tissues therefore await future research.

The lack of a positive effect of empagliflozin on renal function in experimental studies may be due to the insufficient duration of treatment, as long-term studies in humans have clearly demonstrated a beneficial effect of SGLT-2 inhibitor administration. In contrast, a short-term study in patients with FSGS showed no renal benefits after 8 weeks of treatment [45]. Therefore, long-term experimental studies to test this hypothesis are needed.

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Fig. 7. The effect of empagliflozin treatment on proteinuria (A), urine flow (B), plasma urea (C) and plasma creatinine (D) in control spontaneously hypertensive rats (SHR-control, n=8) (black circles), SHR fed a high-fat (SHR+HF, n=10) diet (blue circles) and empagliflozin-treated SHR-HF (SHR+HF+empa, n=10) (red circles). Data are means \pm SEM.

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Hojna: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Hana Rauchová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Hana Malínská:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Michaela Kadlecová:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.biopha.2024.116520](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biopha.2024.116520).

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